

Proof of Millennium Theorem "P versus NP"

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Abstract. We go on towards the proof of concept of Millennium Theorem proposed by Stephen Cook, we state that polynomial classes and its successors like non-polynomial (NP) are equal along the function equilibrium which is justified by the parallel processing law, we will also give the exact algorithm to Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) which is computed in the polynomial complexity time of the product of linear and logarithmic operands, the linear algorithm for the maximum flow problem is also given.

Keywords: computational complexity, P versus NP, Traveling Salesman Problem, maximum flow.

Pre-historical facts. We discuss the main statement and proof made by author of "P versus NP" theorem Stephen Cook - a winner of Alan Mathison Turing Award sponsored by Association of Computing Machinery (ACM). In this notable works [1, 2, 3, 4] he first proofs the existence of unsolvable problems along the divided complexity classes known as polynomial (P) which can be solved in the observed amount of time and non-polynomial (NP) which cannot be solved using the approaches developed up to the present time in the fixed time complexity.

There and onwards this question was raised for more than decades and still remains actual up to the present time. We will show further that practical algorithms exist which solve the NP-hard problem in a meaningful time span on any type of automata using an algorithmic approach.

We will show the proof of concept by proposing first the algorithm to the classical Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) and a linear algorithm to the maximum flow problem [5].

Proof of "P versus NP". We show that P equals NP along the fixed function which coincide two theoretically unequal classes:

$$f(P) = NP.$$

Since the existence of the assumed parallel computing law we get the following:

$$\lim[N \rightarrow \infty] \frac{NP}{N} = P.$$

We substitute the above law formula with the following assumption:

$$\lim[N \rightarrow \infty] \frac{f(P)}{N} = P.$$

Then we get the following:

$$\lim[N \rightarrow \infty][f(P)] = \lim[N \rightarrow \infty][P \cdot N].$$

Since from the above it follows that classes are equal as both sides are equal to the infinity:

$$\begin{aligned}\lim[N \rightarrow \infty][f(P)] &= \infty \\ \lim[N \rightarrow \infty][P \cdot N] &= \infty\end{aligned}$$

Thus, it follows that:

$$f(P) = P \cdot N \Rightarrow NP = P \cdot N \Rightarrow P = NP.$$

Traveling Salesman Problem in almost linear time. From the proof of equivalence of complexity classes it follows that there is a logarithmic-linear algorithm for TSP. We describe this algorithm in a few steps by using the classical Dijkstra approach of finding the shortest path in a connected graph. As the algorithms both are similar, they still have significant differences as for TSP we define the following method of solving this problem in $O(n \cdot \log(n))$: start from the empty set of paths, connect the paths by finding the shortest edge from finish to the start of this path if it doesn't form the cycle, repeat these steps until we get the full Hamiltonian cycle and path.

Maximum Flow in linear time. The linear time complexity for the classical network flow problem follows from the algorithm which can be solved in a few steps by introducing the weight potential method which includes the first step as forming the possible paths along the accumulated potential and minimal from the incoming and outgoing flow for the source and sink of the path along the network - the latter step is to compute the potential for each vertex in a flow.

Conclusion. We have developed stable and minimal in complexity time solutions for the Traveling Salesman Problem and Maximum Flow Problem - which results from the proof of the functional conjecture of the complexity classes along the equivalence function of P and NP. The further steps are to find other polynomial solutions for the problems which weren't practically before.

References

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